

Basic Digital Skills in Desi Countries

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They grew by an average of 3.87% between 2016 and 2021

The DESI Index calculates the value of a variable called “Individuals with basic digital skills”. For individuals with basic digital skills we mean people who have skills in the following four areas, namely: information, communication, problem solving and software for creating content. The data refer to the period between 2016 and 2021 and exclude the United Kingdom.

Ranking of Desi countries by value of basic digital skills in 2021. The Netherlands ranks first by value of individuals with basic digital skills in 2021 with a value of 39.68, followed by Finland with a value of 38.23 units and from Sweden with a value of 36.21 units. In the middle of the table there are Lithuania with a value of 28.07 units, followed by Malta with an amount of 27.91 units and Slovenia with an amount equal to 27.57 units. Italy closes the ranking with an amount of 20.75 units, followed by Romania with an amount of 25.49 units and Bulgaria with an amount of 14.70 units. On average in the Desi countries, the value of individuals with basic digital skills was equal to an amount of 27,907 units in 2021.

Ranking of countries by value of the percentage change in basic digital skills in the period between 2016 and 2021. Ireland ranks first in terms of the percentage change in digital skills with a value equal to 20.28% equal to an amount of 4.5 units, followed by Romania with an amount of 17.88% equal to an amount of 2.35 units and by Greece with a variation equal to an amount of 14.78% equal to an amount of 3.25 units. In the middle of the table there are Luxembourg with an amount of 5.41% equal to an amount of 1.66 units, followed by Germany with an amount of 5.16% equal to an amount of 1.72 units and Croatia with an amount of amount of 4.79% equal to an amount of 1.22 units. Bulgaria closes the ranking with a value equal to -5.81% equal to a value of -0.91 units, followed by Denmark with a value equal to -6.58% equal to an amount of -2.46 units, and from Latvia with a value equal to -12.67% equal to an amount of -3.12 units.

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Competenze Digitali di Base nei Paesi Desi

Countries	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Var Ass	Var Per
Austria	★ 32,00	★ 32,73	★ 33,72	★ 33,72	★ 32,78	★ 32,78	★ 0,77	★ 2,42
Belgium	★ 30,14	★ 30,45	★ 30,28	★ 30,28	★ 30,42	★ 30,42	★ 0,27	★ 0,91
Bulgaria	★ 15,61	★ 13,12	★ 14,75	★ 14,75	★ 14,70	★ 14,70	★ -0,91	★ -5,81
Croatia	★ 25,46	★ 27,31	★ 26,99	★ 26,99	★ 26,68	★ 26,68	★ 1,22	★ 4,79
Cyprus	★ 21,27	★ 21,46	★ 25,19	★ 25,19	★ 22,51	★ 22,51	★ 1,24	★ 5,82
Czechia	★ 28,45	★ 26,90	★ 29,92	★ 29,92	★ 31,05	★ 31,05	★ 2,60	★ 9,14
Denmark	★ 37,46	★ 38,78	★ 35,60	★ 35,60	★ 34,99	★ 34,99	★ -2,46	★ -6,58
Estonia	★ 32,26	★ 30,16	★ 30,16	★ 30,16	★ 30,79	★ 30,79	★ -1,47	★ -4,55
Finland	★ 36,99	★ 36,53	★ 37,78	★ 37,78	★ 38,23	★ 38,23	★ 1,25	★ 3,37
France	★ 28,39	★ 27,82	★ 28,56	★ 28,56	★ 28,65	★ 28,65	★ 0,26	★ 0,91
Germany	★ 33,36	★ 33,77	★ 34,09	★ 34,09	★ 35,08	★ 35,08	★ 1,72	★ 5,16
Greece	★ 22,01	★ 22,92	★ 23,08	★ 23,08	★ 25,26	★ 25,26	★ 3,25	★ 14,78
Hungary	★ 24,76	★ 25,68	★ 24,80	★ 24,80	★ 24,34	★ 24,34	★ -0,42	★ -1,69
Ireland	★ 22,19	★ 22,09	★ 23,82	★ 23,82	★ 26,69	★ 26,69	★ 4,50	★ 20,28
Italy	★ 21,65	★ 21,83	★ 21,29	★ 21,29	★ 20,75	★ 20,75	★ -0,90	★ -4,14
Latvia	★ 24,60	★ 25,18	★ 24,04	★ 24,04	★ 21,48	★ 21,48	★ -3,12	★ -12,67
Lithuania	★ 25,62	★ 25,80	★ 27,39	★ 27,39	★ 28,07	★ 28,07	★ 2,46	★ 9,58
Luxembourg	★ 30,63	★ 31,09	★ 31,66	★ 31,66	★ 32,29	★ 32,29	★ 1,66	★ 5,41
Malta	★ 26,34	★ 24,80	★ 28,30	★ 28,30	★ 27,91	★ 27,91	★ 1,57	★ 5,95
Netherlands	★ 36,21	★ 38,25	★ 39,75	★ 39,75	★ 39,68	★ 39,68	★ 3,47	★ 9,58
Poland	★ 20,02	★ 22,21	★ 23,19	★ 23,19	★ 22,22	★ 22,22	★ 2,20	★ 11,01
Portugal	★ 23,81	★ 23,82	★ 25,13	★ 25,13	★ 25,88	★ 25,88	★ 2,07	★ 8,68
Romania	★ 13,14	★ 13,83	★ 14,52	★ 14,52	★ 15,49	★ 15,49	★ 2,35	★ 17,88
Slovakia	★ 26,57	★ 27,63	★ 29,51	★ 29,51	★ 26,93	★ 26,93	★ 0,36	★ 1,36
Slovenia	★ 25,45	★ 26,46	★ 27,00	★ 27,00	★ 27,57	★ 27,57	★ 2,12	★ 8,31
Spain	★ 26,95	★ 26,67	★ 27,38	★ 27,38	★ 28,60	★ 28,60	★ 1,65	★ 6,13
Sweden	★ 35,79	★ 34,32	★ 38,60	★ 38,60	★ 36,21	★ 36,21	★ 0,42	★ 1,17

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The data show the presence of three clusters, namely:

- Cluster 1: Portugal, Hungary, Slovenia, Croatia, Lithuania, Ireland, Latvia, Greece, Malta, Cyprus, Spain, Poland, Slovakia, France, Italy, Czech Republic;
- Cluster 2: Finland, Sweden, Germany, Denmark, the Netherlands, Austria, Luxembourg, Estonia, Belgium;
- Cluster 3: Romania, Bulgaria.

From the metric point of view it is possible to verify that the median value of Cluster 2-C2 is equal to an amount of 33.88 units, the value of the median of Cluster 1-C1 is equal to an amount of 26.68 units and the value of Cluster 3-C3 is equal to an amount of 15.09 units. Therefore, the following ordering of the clusters derives, namely: $C2 = 33.88 > C1 = 26.68 > C3 = 15.09$. From a geographical point of view it appears that the Scandinavian countries and Northern Europe have the highest levels of basic digital skills. This indicator therefore confirms the dominance of Northern Europe over

Central, Southern and Eastern Europe in terms of technological advancements and human capital formation.

Network Analysis with the Manhattan Distance. A network analysis is applied below using the Manhattan distance. A complex network structure is detected, i.e. consisting of more than two nodes, and a simplified network structure consisting of only two nodes. There is a complex network structure consisting of France, Spain, Slovenia, Lithuania, Malta and Croatia. Particularly:

- France has a connection with Spain for a value of 0.29 units;
- Spain has a connection with France for a value of 0.29 units, with Slovenia for a value of 0.22 units, with Lithuania for a value of 0.19 units, with Malta for a value of 0.28, with Croatia for a value of 0.3;
- Slovenia has a connection with Spain for a value of 0.22 units, with Lithuania for a value of 0.12 units, and with Croatia for a value of 0.14 units;
- Lithuania has a connection with Slovenia for a value of 0.12 units, with Spain for a value of 0.19 units, with Malta for a value of 0.21, and with Croatia for a value equal to 0.25;
- Malta has a connection with Spain for a value of 0.28, with Lithuania with a value of 0.21;
- Croatia has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.25 units, with Spain for a value of 0.3 units and with Slovenia for a value of 0.14 units.

It follows that Spain is the country with the greatest connections in the dynamics of the evolution of the variable "Basic Digital Skills".

There are also three simplified network structures or consisting of only two nodes as indicated below:

- Greece and Ireland have a connection equal to a value of 0.23;
- Estonia and Belgium are connected by a link with a value of 0.25;
- Hungary and Portugal are connected by a link equal to a value of 0.3 units.

Conclusions. The value of the basic digital skills variable grew on average by about 4% in the period between 2016 and 2021. However, this is an insufficient value to generate a workforce capable of operating with the tools and techniques of industry 4.0. Certainly, however, cluster analysis highlights the European heterogeneity. Scandinavian and Northern European countries have the highest levels of basic digital skills. Action is needed to increase the value of basic digital skills, especially in the countries of southern and eastern Europe. In fact, for the transition to industry 4.0 to be fully achieved, both in the public and private sectors, it is necessary to increase even basic digital skills. Furthermore, since the digital economy is a component of the knowledge economy, it follows that the dissemination of basic digital skills allows for the generation of human capital capable of creating the conditions for new economic growth in the economy of intangibles.

Declarations

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